

MAGNETISM AND CATALYSIS. PART I. CATALYTIC DECOMPOSITION OF POTASSIUM CHLORATE BY MANGANESE DIOXIDE AND FERRIC OXIDE.

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The reaction mechanism of the catalysed decomposition of potassium chlorate with oxides are examined from the magnetic standpoint by a chemical and magnetic analysis of the products at different stages of the reaction by measurements of χ . The mechanism has been proved to involve the formation of an intermediate compound as shown by differences at the intervening stages of the reaction between the observed values of χ and the values calculated on the mixture law. The nature of the possible intermediate compound is discussed and the earlier theories are controverted. A modified form of Sodeau's theory of alternate oxidation and deoxidation is suggested. In the case of catalysis by ferric oxide, strict concordance is evinced between the observed and the calculated values of χ at all stages of the reaction.

It was observed by Hedvall, Hedin and Persson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1934, **B27**, 196) that the thermal decomposition of nitrous oxide, using nickel as a catalyst, was suddenly accelerated above the Curie point, although X-ray analysis by Nunzio (*Atti. R. Inst. Veneto*, 1933, **92**, 541) does not indicate any change in lattice-structure above this temperature. An extension of the work by Hedvall and others (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1937, **B30**, 280) has shown that the hydrogenation of carbon monoxide and acetylene in the presence of nickel, and the formation of CO_2 from CO by Heusler's alloy is considerably accelerated at the Curie point. Forestier and Lille (*Compt. rend.*, 1937, **204**, 265, 1254) who studied the catalytic power of ferrites of Mg, Cu, Sr, Ba and Pb, found anomalies at the Curie point accompanied by a marked rise in catalytic power in the neighbourhood of this temperature. The fact that catalytic activity may have some relation to magnetic properties was also emphasised by Taylor and Diamond (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1251), who found that the spin isomerisation of hydrogen at low temperatures is much more catalysed by a paramagnetic surface than by a diamagnetic one. Apart from this little use has been made of the magnetic method in deciding the mechanism of the catalytic changes, particularly those where the formation of an intermediate compound is postulated.

A case in point is the catalysed decomposition of potassium chlorate with oxides. It has been suggested from time to time that the action is

purely mechanical but if it were so, all other finely divided substances, irrespective of their chemical composition, should be expected to act in a similar manner which, however, is not the case. Besides, a microscopic examination of MnO_2 , before and after the reaction, shows that the dioxide has undergone a physical change which leads to the conclusion that the forces involved in the reaction are chemical in nature. If the decomposition takes place *via* an intermediate compound, then its formation (if it is stable) in the intermediate stages, even though it may not be revealed by chemical analysis, would be shown by magnetic analysis of the reaction products particularly if the development of the new compound entails changes in valency. That changes in valency produce corresponding changes in magnetic moment which can be correlated with atomic structure, has been emphasised by several workers, notably Van Vleck ("Theory of Electric and Magnetic Susceptibilities," Oxford, particularly Chapter XI, p. 73), Sommerfeld ("Atombau," 4th Edition, p. 639), Bose (*Z. Physik.*, 1927, 43, 864) and Stoner (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929, 8, 250) who have obtained the following relationship in the case of the paramagnetic ions of transition elements :

$$\mu_B = \sqrt{4S(S+1)},$$

the value of μ_B depending on S and ultimately on the valency of the ion.

The main object of the present investigation is to ascertain the reaction mechanism by a magnetic and chemical analysis of the products at various stages of the reaction and to test the validity of the numerous theories of this action which have been advanced from time to time.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The susceptibility values were determined on a modified form of Gouy's magnetic balance and the calculation of χ made according to the equation,

$$\chi_{p_2} = \frac{1}{m_{p_1}} \left\{ (\chi_{p_1} m_{p_1} - \chi_a m_{ap_1}) \frac{W_{p_2}}{W_{p_1}} + \chi_a m_{ap_2} \right\}$$

where χ_{p_1} and χ_{p_2} are respectively the specific susceptibilities of the standard substance and of the specimen, W_{p_1} and W_{p_2} are the respective pulls, m_{p_1} and m_{p_2} are the respective masses and m_{ap_1} and m_{ap_2} are the masses of air displaced respectively by the standard substance and by the specimen.

Materials Used.

Potassium Chlorate.—The extra pure salt was recrystallised and its purity ascertained by reducing it to the chloride with sulphur dioxide and estimating the chloride by Volhard's method (% purity = 99.80). The chlorate gave a susceptibility value of -0.300×10^{-6} (cf. $\chi = -0.300$, International Critical Tables).

Manganese Dioxide.—Many attempts have been made to obtain pure manganese dioxide and it has been shown that it cannot be obtained pure by any of the precipitation methods since the hydrated dioxide very readily loses part of its oxygen and thus forms mixtures of oxides. Various other methods for the preparation of MnO_2 were examined and ultimately the catalyst was prepared by heating manganous nitrate at $155-60^\circ$ for 50 hours. The black crystalline oxide was washed and dried under vacuum at 200° . Its oxidising power was determined by treating the oxide with hydrochloric acid. The chlorine liberated was absorbed in potassium iodide solution and the iodine thus set free titrated against standard thiosulphate. The total manganese was determined by the pyrophosphate method. The product was found to conform to the formula $MnO_{1.97}$ and its susceptibility was found to be 29.00×10^{-6} at 20° . Literature, however, reports divergent values varying between 27.00 and 46.58×10^{-6} for the dioxide (Meyer, *Wied. Ann.*, 1899, **68**, 325; **69**, 236; *Ann. Physik*, 1900, **1**, 664; Wistrand, "Magnetiska Susceptibilitaten hos Kvarts etc." Upsala 1916; Wedekind and Horst, *Ber.*, 1915, **48**, 105). These values have been more fully discussed in a separate communication which will shortly be published.

Ferric Oxide.—The hydroxide was precipitated by adding ammonia to ferric chloride and the product dehydrated at 500° in an electric furnace. (Found: Fe, 69.8%; calc. 70.0%). The observed susceptibility for the oxide was 21.00×10^{-6} at 20° (cf. $\chi_{Fe_2O_3} = 20.6 \times 10^{-6}$ at 18° , International Critical Tables).

The susceptibility of an intimate mixture of potassium chlorate and the catalyst approximately in the ratio of 4 : 1, was determined after analysis. It was then heated at different temperatures (below the temperature of spontaneous ignition) for different intervals of time, its χ determined and the products analysed at each stage. The methods of analyses are given below.

Chloride and Chlorate.—The mixture was treated with water till free of chloride and chlorate and the filtrate made up to known volume. Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method and the chlorate was reduced to chloride in an aliquot portion with sulphur dioxide and the chloride determined as above.

Analyses.

Manganese was estimated by the pyrophosphate method and the active oxygen determined in the insoluble residue iodometrically.

Ferric oxide was estimated by precipitation as hydroxide followed by ignition to Fe_2O_3 .

The results, so obtained, are set forth in Tables I and II, the χ -value in each case representing the mean of at least three observations.

Since the composition of the mixture and the susceptibility of its components at various stages are known, the theoretical value of χ is that arrived at on the additivity law for a mixture.

TABLE I.

Catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate with manganese dioxide.

$$\begin{aligned}\chi_{\text{MnO}_2} &= 29.00 \times 10^{-6} \\ \chi_{\text{KCl}} &= -0.516 \times 10^{-6} \\ \chi_{\text{KClO}_3} &= -0.300 \times 10^{-6}\end{aligned}$$

MIXTURE I.

Reading.	Temp. heating	Time.	Composition of the solid residue.				$\chi \times 10^6$		Diff. (a-b) $\times 10^6$.
			MnO ₂	KClO ₃	KCl	Total.	Exp. (a)	Calc. (b)	
1	18.80%	81.06%	0.00%	99.86%	5.20	5.21	-0.01
2	250-260°C	0.5 hr.	19.71	76.92	3.25	99.88	5.23	5.47	-0.24
3	270-280°	1.0	21.10	58.49	20.25	99.84	5.59	5.84	-0.25
4	290-300°	1.0	22.75	42.01	35.12	99.88	6.03	6.29	-0.26
5	300-310°	1.0	25.10	23.89	51.00	99.99	6.69	6.94	-0.25
6	320-330°	Spontaneous	27.20	0.00	72.63	99.83	7.53	7.51	+0.02

MIXTURE II.

1	18.80	81.06	0.00	99.86	5.20	5.21	-0.01
2	250-260°	0.5	19.68	77.05	3.16	99.89	5.21	5.46	-0.25
3	270-280°	1.0	21.13	58.41	20.31	99.85	5.58	5.85	-0.27
4	290-300°	1.0	22.76	42.03	35.21	100.00	6.05	6.30	-0.25
5	300-310°	1.0	25.03	23.86	51.03	99.92	6.69	6.92	-0.23
6	320-330°	Spontaneous	27.22	0.00	72.65	99.87	7.51	7.52	-0.01

TABLE II.

Catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate with ferric oxide.

$$\chi_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} = 21.00 \times 10^{-6}.$$

MIXTURE I.

Reading.	Temp.	Time.	Composition of the solid residue			Total.	$\chi \times 10^6$		Diff. (a-b) $\times 10^6$.
							Exp.	Calc.	
1	20.45%	79.35%	0.00%	99.80%	4.05	4.06	-0.01
2	250-260°	0.5 hrs.	21.00	75.03	3.73	99.76	4.19	4.17	+0.02
3	290-300°	1.0	22.13	64.47	13.17	99.77	4.36	4.39	-0.03
4	300-310°	1.0	23.85	50.20	25.51	99.56	4.70	4.73	-0.03
5	310-320°	1.0	26.30	23.51	50.03	99.84	5.19	5.19	-0.00
6	340-350°	Spontaneous	29.40	0.00	70.33	99.73	5.82	5.82	+0.01

MIXTURE II.

1	20.45	79.35	0.00	99.80	4.05	4.06	-0.01
2	250-260°	0.5	20.95	75.15	3.65	99.75	4.17	4.16	+0.01
3	290-300°	1.0	22.20	64.24	13.36	99.80	4.40	4.40	0.00
4	300-310°	1.0	23.90	50.11	25.73	99.74	4.71	4.74	-0.03
5	310-320°	1.0	26.33	23.60	50.13	100.06	5.18	5.20	-0.02
6	340-350°	Spontaneous	29.43	0.00	70.29	99.72	5.82	5.82	0.00

DISCUSSION.

The numerous theories which have been advanced from time to time in order to explain the reaction mechanism of the catalysed decomposition with manganese dioxide are essentially (a) mechanical, and (b) chemical in nature.

The mechanical hypothesis has been dealt with earlier (*vide supra*). While studying the catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate by oxides and metals Psarshevski (*Sci. Mag. Chem. Cath. Katerinoslav*, 1926, p. 165) remarked that their action is due to a mechanical disturbance of the equilibrium of the electrons of the chlorate molecule. It is supposed that the

absorbed gases are ionised by the impact of electrons of the catalyst and thereafter act upon the salt. The magnetic results, however, leave no doubt about the formation of an intermediate compound and hence it appears that manganese dioxide actively takes part in the kinetics of the reaction. Any chemical explanation must be of the nature of a cycle of changes which ultimately result in the release of the dioxide.

It is to be noted that the observed paramagnetic susceptibility of the reaction mixtures (*vide* Table I) at the intermediate stages is lower than the value calculated on the mixture law and consequently the alleged intermediate compound must be either diamagnetic or at least less strongly paramagnetic than the original dioxide.

Wachter's hypothesis which postulates the development of manganous salts as intermediate compounds consequently involves an increase in paramagnetism, since on the Bose-Stoner formula

$$\sqrt{\mu_B} = 4S(S+1),$$

Mn²⁺ and Mn³⁺ ions have magnetic moments of 5.92 and 3.87 Bohr units respectively is therefore ruled out.

The evolution of traces of chlorine which accompany these changes, however, led McLeod to propose the following scheme of reaction:

the permanganate next breaks up according to the equation,

and ultimately this is followed by

In this scheme the liberation of free chlorine necessitates the formation of an equivalent amount of potassium oxide or possibly permanganate or manganate in the free state. The observed deviation of susceptibility from the calculated values as recorded in Table I should *a priori* be due to the formation of one or more of these compounds, and since on McLeod's mechanism these compounds are progressively formed with increased evolution of free chlorine at every stage, the observed susceptibility values ought to show a continuous decrease all through, the maximum differences being obtained at the final stage. This is contrary to the present observations. Moreover, the amount of potassium permanganate or oxide that can be formed equivalent to the chlorine actually liberated, is totally inadequate to account for the marked lowering of susceptibility observed here, its contribution being barely to the extent of $0.01 - 0.02 \times 10^{-6}$, whereas the observed difference is in the neighbourhood of 0.25×10^{-6} .

Deniges (*Bull. trav. Soc. Pharm. Bordeaux*, 1936, 74, 93) has shown from spectroscopic evidence that MnO_4 ion is developed in the course of this reaction but he definitely precludes the possibility of potassium permanganate formation, since $KMnO_4$ was found to exercise no catalytic influence on the decomposition. He, however, holds manganese permanganate that may have been formed in course of the reaction responsible for the accelerated reaction velocity. It is, however, by no means certain that manganous permanganate is actually developed in the reaction. Magnetic considerations, in fact, seem to invalidate its formation. Although theoretically on the Bose-Stoner formula, manganous permanganate should be less strongly paramagnetic than manganese dioxide containing quadrivalent manganese $\{\chi_{Mn(MnO_4)_2} = 4940 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\chi_{MnO_2} = 6350 \times 10^{-6}\}$, yet it is well known that the magnetic behaviour of MnO_2 deviates widely from the theoretical and the deviation is towards lesser paramagnetism $\{\chi_{MnO_2}$ (Exptl.) = $2520 \times 10^{-6}\}$. The formation of $Mn(MnO_4)_2$ will, in consequence, produce greater paramagnetism than the calculated values indicate at the intervening stages of the reaction.

The following scheme, which involves the separation of potassium and chlorine, through the formation of a complex, possibly of the Werner type, is tentatively suggested.

The formation of these complexes readily explains the magnetic results. On theory, hepta- or hexa-valency of manganese will obviously result in lowering of paramagnetic susceptibility. The formation of MnO_7^- ,—as observed spectroscopically by Deniges (*loc. cit.*) and of the different oxides of manganese the formation and breaking up of which according to Sodeau are responsible for the catalytic activity, follow as the direct consequence of the side-reaction in this cycle.

In the case of the reaction catalysed by Fe_2O_3 , close concordance is obtained between the observed and the calculated values of χ as recorded in Table II. The reaction may involve electronic disturbances of the type proposed by Psarshevski (*loc. cit.*) in which the activation energy supplied by the catalyst molecule is regained by it after the chlorate molecule has

undergone dissociation. Fowler and Grant (*Trans. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 277) conclude from the close agreement of its mode of action with that of manganese dioxide that an analogous reaction takes place, involving the formation of intermediate products. If this is so, the intermediate compound so formed must be very unstable. since no deviations from the mixture law have been observed though the possibility of a relatively stable intermediary, which may result in the mixture having the same susceptibility all through, should not be precluded.

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